

THEORETICAL POETICS AS A BASIS FOR DIFFERENTIATION OF TEACHING LITERATURE

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The term "poetics" has many meanings in literary criticism. A brief history of the various meanings of this concept is given by V. E. Khalizev [1, 143-145]. We will adhere to the meaning of poetics, which was determined by B. Tomashevsky; V. Tomashevsky. According to him, poetics is a branch of literary criticism, the subject of which is the composition, structure and function of works, as well as literary types and genres [2, 25-26]. We are primarily interested in the theoretical concept of poetics, reflected in the school curriculum in literature. According to M.M. Bakhtin, in the composition of works of art has two aspects. Firstly, external material work (in literature these are sounds and words), expressed by the term artifact, and, secondly, such an aesthetic object that has the potential to have an artistic impact on the reader. The aesthetic object, so to speak, is contained in the artifact and, to some extent, is revealed to the mind of the reader. The world of art or artistic creativity is not a continuum, but is divided into “separate, self-contained, individual wholes – works” that “take an independent position in relation to reality” [3, 280].

On the one hand, works can be combined into cycles, and as a result of such integration, new works may appear that combine previously created ones. In the school literature curriculum, this is “Poems about the Beautiful Lady” by A.A. Blok, “Notes of a Hunter” by I.S. Turgenev and Belkin's Tale by A.S. Pushkin. It is important to develop an understanding that each of the above works is both independent and part of a larger artistic whole. This helps to comprehend from each work in the context of the entire cycle, the author's work, the literary period, that is, in the historical and cultural context, without which the "astute reader" is inconceivable.

On the other hand, each part of the work has the features of the whole and at the same time represents a kind of independence. This is important when teaching literature in schools. After all, one of the most important tasks in the final exams is the interpretation of parts of a literary work. For a complete understanding of the text, it is important that students realize that some literary works are not complete (for example, “Who lives well in Russia” by N. A. Nekrasov) or that the published texts do not fully correspond to the author's intention (for example, “Eugene Onegin” A S. Pushkin in his connection with Onegin's Travels and Chapter 10). In addition, some works or parts of works have author's versions, and different editions, the study of which may lead to the creation of a differentiated task of a comparative nature.

When studying literary works at school, their content is first analyzed, and the artistic form is discussed in passing, without disclosing the function of the specific elements that make up their structure; this is how literature textbooks were written from the 30s - 70s of the twentieth century, but the concept of an essential form in Russian literary criticism was created in the 20s by M.M. Bakhtin. MM Bakhtin argued that the form has no meaning outside of its correlation with the content. “In every smallest element of the poetic structure, in every metaphor, in every epithet,” writes M.M. Bakhtin, “we will find a chemical combination of cognitive definition, ethical assessment and artistic finalization” [4, 156-157].

V.E. Khalizev identifies three aspects of the content form. This is an objective principle associated with the world of a work of art, artistic speech and composition. However, the content

is embodied as the sum of the individual elements that make up the form, so Yu.M. Lotman writes that "the idea is not contained in any one quotation, even if it is well chosen, but is expressed in its entire artistic structure" [5, 37-38]. In school practice, especially in the humanities, differentiated tasks are possible to understand the content of the form and determine the function of the structure of the work.

A complex and important aspect of teaching school literature is the study of the artistic world of the work and the artistic world of the author. It is no coincidence that in many school literature programs these formulations are placed at the beginning of the chapter on the work of Russian classics in the senior classes. The concept of the artistic world of a work, as D.S. Likhachev substantiated, is created according to the laws established by the artist himself [6, 121]. W. Eco says about his novel "The Name of the Rose" that "The writer is a prisoner of his own premises" [7, 438-439]. The world of the work is "an artistically mastered and transformed reality". As part of the artistic world, there is a system of images and events from which the plot is built. The most important elements of the artistic world are the components of figurativeness. These are actions, portraits, situations of characters and the realities of the world around them (landscape, interior). It is the speech actions and details of the characters that occupy an important place in the artistic world of the work [8, 158]. Therefore, in school practice, differentiated tasks for the study of individual components of the text are possible, motivated by the personal interests of students and the need to develop certain aspects of their literary education. Such tasks can be of varying degrees of complexity, for example, related to the narrator, lyrical hero, characters or the image of the author. More complex tasks relate to the study of the inner world of a person and its embodiment in literature.

The study of the dynamics of a person's experiences, his states describing them in verbal images, is perhaps the most difficult part of studying literature at school. To do this, it is necessary to determine the ways of describing the inner life of the characters, to explore their impressions of the environment, their state of mind, dreams, dreams and internal monologues. The basis for differentiation is the student's personal motivation and his interest in the manifestations of a person's psychological states.

For example, when analyzing a portrait of a hero, it is important how the figure appears in the portrait: idealized or grotesque, in the words of the writer or one of the heroes, integrally or "scattered" throughout the work. In the literature of the 19th century, the portrait began to be filled with psychological content, the portrait became significant, its changes as it matured. It is very interesting to study the forms of behavior of the characters, the peculiarities of their speech, their objective world, their psychological landscape, which plays an important role in determining the state of the inner world of the characters.

Advanced tasks concern mastering the artistic functions of space and time. These are observations on biographical, historical, cosmic, calendar and everyday images of time. These are the concepts of dynamics and statics, past, present and future. When studying artistic space, it is important to determine whether it is closed or open, real or imaginary, near or far, and to explain the artistic function of these images, since "any entry into the sphere of meanings is accomplished only through the gates of chronotopes" [9/3, 406].

The interest of students in studying the plot of a work is associated not only with the elements of the work (the lowest level of complexity), but also with the search for information about real events on which the work is based, the author's biography, the concept of "wandering

plot" and the task of comparing the work with mythological or biblical plots (higher level of difficulty). It is also important to find ways to portray the drama, dynamics, and conflicts of the plot. The most difficult part of the tasks is the definition of the author's style, the search for the characteristics of a period or literary movement, or the disclosure of the cultural context of the work. There are several different types of literary research that can be used to determine an author's style: school research on hidden allusions, style and parody, literary references. This level of complexity can also be implemented in the tasks of the Literary Olympiad.

In recent years, the study of works in their cultural context has become increasingly important in school education. In high school, "the immediate context of a literary work" can be recognized [10/8, 291]. This includes the creative history of the work, the biography of the author, and comparison of drafts or final versions of the work with its fragments. In the humanities, one can turn to facts relating to the social and cultural life of the author and his contemporaries, the study of historical time, literary traditions and their violations, the worldview and confession of the author and their relationship with views on the state, property. Myths and Bible stories can be studied as individual assignments. The better students understand the connections between a work and its various contexts, the greater the scope for analysis and interpretation. Unfortunately, the time allotted for teaching literature in schools is limited. However, a differentiated approach for students with different interests and levels of literary development can broaden this framework by encouraging interest in independent activity and homework research.

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